

A STUDY OF COMPRESSION LOADED HAT-STIFFENED COMPOSITE PANELS

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ABSTRACT

The use of composite materials in the primary structure of aircraft is becoming more common. Stiffened composite panels have been designed for a variety of load carrying conditions in aircraft. In this study, design considerations and manufacturing techniques for hat-stiffened composite panels were investigated. The curing manufacturing technique was used to produce the stiffened composite panel. Ultrasonic C-scan inspections were carried out to detect any defects in the panel. The panel was tested in compression to verify its structural efficiency. The panel was designed to carry loads after the initiation of skin buckling. Both the buckling and post-buckling behavior were predicted using the finite element method. Eight-node 3-D laminated composite general shell elements were used in the analysis. The predicted buckling load and post-buckling response were compared with the test data. The buckling load of the stiffeners was also predicted by the finite element method and this load was considered as the failure load of the panel. In addition to the analysis and test results, this paper also presents the details of the laminate design and testing procedures.

INTRODUCTION

Current use of advanced composites in aircraft structures has demonstrated the potential for decreasing structural weight. Weight savings result from the high stiffness-to-density and high strength-to-density properties of fibres such as carbon. Also, weight may be saved by tailoring the ply orientations of laminated composites to meet the structural needs.

In conventional aircraft applications, it is a common practice to design stiffened metallic plate and shell structures to buckle below design ultimate load. Post-buckled design allows buckling before design limit load is reached and the buckled structure can carry design ultimate load. Panels are frequently designed to carry loads that are three or four times the initial buckling load [1]. Usually, the post-buckled design results in a significant weight saving when compared to buckling-resistant design. This paper is concerned with the analysis, fabrication and testing of composite panels with hat-shape stiffeners. Predicted and experimental initial buckling loads and post-buckled response of these composite panels under compression loading are also presented and discussed.

DESIGN AND MANUFACTURE OF HAT-STIFFENED COMPOSITE PANEL

In a previous study of stiffened composite panels by the Structures, Materials and Propulsion Laboratory of IAR [1], a literature search revealed that the design of the ply orientation and the number of plies depend on load magnitude and direction. Design and analysis studies of stiffened panels have been conducted by many researchers [2,3,4,5], and some of their conclusions follow;

- a. the outer plies should be $\pm 45^\circ$ for all elements of the structure to carry the shear loads,
- b. at least one 0-degree ply (parallel to the load) should be adjacent to the outer ($\pm 45^\circ$) plies,
- c. it is more efficient to place the 90-degree plies next to the 0-degree plies (these 90° plies greatly improve the junctures between elements by providing resistance to out-of-plane displacements, thus both buckling and post-buckled strengths are increased),
- d. the use of 0° plies in the cap and skin would improve the structural efficiency, but the number of these 0° plies should be carefully calculated to meet the design loads,
- e. the webs should be as near perpendicular to the skin as is possible in order to reduce peeling stresses in the flange-skin interface, and
- f. to minimize distortion, the plies should be oriented symmetrically about the mid-plane of the various elements.

Based on [1] and the above guidelines, a stiffened panel configuration consisting of a flat 12-ply skin and three equally spaced longitudinal hat-shape stiffeners, having a web of 12 plies, a flange of 5 plies and cap of 24 plies was designed. Figure 1 shows the geometry, dimensions and stacking sequence of the panel.

The composite material used in this study was unidirectional tape of Hercules IM6 carbon fibre pre-impregnated with Narmco 5245C resin. Typical mechanical properties of this material are presented in Table 1. The panel was manufactured using a cocuring technique.

The panel was ultrasonically inspected using C-Scan in both the pulse-echo and reflection pulse-echo modes; no significant defects were detected. The loaded ends of the panel were machined to a flatness tolerance of 0.1 mm and a parallel-end tolerance of 0.2 mm. After machining, the ends of the panel were potted into steel U-shape channels with epoxy resin. The channels acted as moulds and also served as end plates for transferring the load to the panel.

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

MODELLING

Finite element analyses were conducted to predict the linear buckling loads, nonlinear post-buckling response, and the failure load of the panel. The commercial finite element code, NISA, was used for the analyses. The 3-D laminated composite general shell element was used in the modeling. This element contains a number of perfectly bonded lamina and the element stiffness properties were calculated based on the classical laminated plate theory. Each node of the element had six degrees of freedom (three translations and three rotations). The whole panel was modeled using a total of 864 8-node quadrilateral elements with 2566 degrees of freedom, as shown in Figure 2. The compressive loading was applied by imposing a uniform displacement downwards on the top line of nodes while the bottom line of nodes was fixed. The total of the

reaction forces from the bottom line of nodes was considered as the applied load under a specified end shortening. Since loaded and reaction ends of the panel were potted in a resin, the ends were not rigidly clamped, therefore the boundary conditions in the model were assumed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\text{at the lower left corner node} && \mathbf{u}_x = \mathbf{u}_y = \mathbf{u}_z = \mathbf{0} \\
 &\text{at the bottom line of nodes} && \mathbf{u}_y = \mathbf{u}_z = \mathbf{0} \\
 &\text{at the top line of nodes} && \mathbf{u}_z = \mathbf{0}, \quad \mathbf{u}_y = -\delta \\
 &\text{at other nodes on potted elements} && \mathbf{u}_z = \mathbf{0}
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where \mathbf{u}_x , \mathbf{u}_y , and \mathbf{u}_z are the displacements in the coordinate directions, and δ is the specified end shortening.

LINEAR BUCKLING ANALYSIS

In the NISA code, linear buckling is a two-pass analysis. The first pass is a static analysis which determines the internal stresses and the applied load P_o under the specified end shortening. The second pass is an eigenvalue analysis which calculates the buckling loads by solving the following eigenvalue equation:

$$\mathbf{K} \mathbf{u} = \lambda \mathbf{K}_g \mathbf{u} \tag{2}$$

where \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{K}_g are the stiffness and geometric stiffness matrices, respectively, \mathbf{u} is the nodal displacement vector which represents the buckling mode shapes, and λ is the load factor which, multiplying the referenced applied load, gives the buckling load as:

$$P_{cr} = \lambda P_o \tag{3}$$

The conventional sub-space iteration technique was employed to solve Eq. (2) for the lowest 15 eigenvalues and modes in this analysis. These eigenmodes were found to be associated with the skin buckling, i.e., the local buckling.

POST-BUCKLING ANALYSIS

The post-buckling behaviour of the panel was investigated through geometric nonlinear analysis. The end shortening was increased step by step until the full shortening was applied. At each step, the following equilibrium equations were established:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{K}_t \Delta \mathbf{u}^{(i)} &= \mathbf{p}_{t+\Delta t} - \mathbf{f}_{t+\Delta t}^{(i-1)} \\
 \mathbf{u}_{t+\Delta t}^{(i)} &= \mathbf{u}_{t+\Delta t}^{(i-1)} + \Delta \mathbf{u}
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

where \mathbf{K}_t is the tangential stiffness matrix at the current step, $\Delta \mathbf{u}^{(i)}$ is the iterative increment of nodal displacements in the i -th iteration, $\mathbf{u}_{t+\Delta t}^{(i)}$, $\mathbf{u}_{t+\Delta t}^{(i-1)}$ are the nodal displacements at step $t+\Delta t$ corresponding to the i -th and $(i-1)$ th iteration, respectively, $\mathbf{p}_{t+\Delta t}$ is the load vector at step $t+\Delta t$, and $\mathbf{f}_{t+\Delta t}^{(i-1)}$ is the vector of internal stresses at step $t+\Delta t$ and iteration $(i-1)$.

The Newton-Raphson method was used to solve Eq. (4) iteratively. Before the first local buckling load (end shortening < 0.381 mm), equal and relatively large step sizes were employed in the computation so that the computing time could be reduced. Beyond that, an automatic selection of the step sizes was used with a relatively small initial step size. This process of selection was based on the convergence of computations in the previous step. The maximum end shortening of 16 mm was used.

The back-to-back strains at some representative locations of the panel were computed and plotted against the loading history. This plotting showed the post-buckling behaviour as well as the local buckling loads.

FAILURE PREDICTION

It is recognized that the major load would be carried by the stiffeners after the skin buckles. Therefore the whole panel is assumed to be failed once the stiffeners buckle and the global buckling load is considered as the failure load of the panel.

To determine the global buckling load, the bending moments at two representative nodes of a stiffener were computed and plotted against the loading history in Figure 3. It is seen that in the initial stage before the skin buckles, there is no bending moment at the nodes. After the skin buckles, the bending moments in the stiffener increase slightly and remain at a relatively low level. A drastic increase in these bending moments indicates that there is a buckling of the stiffener which implies the total collapse of the panel.

EXPERIMENT

STRAIN AND DEFLECTION MEASUREMENT

Based on a literature survey [1], the maximum out-of-plane displacement of this type of stiffened composite panel would likely occur in the centre bay of the panel, near the mid-length. Hence most of the strain gauges were bonded to the mid-length area of the panel in order to capture critical strains in the buckled and post-buckled states. The selection of locations for the strain gauges was based on the preliminary assumption that they would be on the expected peaks and valleys of the buckled skin. Also, back-to-back axial gauges were selected for all the locations, except for those on the webs, to monitor the initial buckling. The gauges located on the webs were in a shear pair configuration.

A shadow Moiré technique was utilized to determine the out-of-plane deformations (buckling patterns) of the test panel. Axial deflections of the test panel during the test were recorded by the test machine data acquisition system and were plotted against the axial loads after the test. A typical load-axial displacement curve is shown in Figure 4.

TESTING

The panel was tested in an MTS test machine (Model 880). The test panel was placed vertically on a flat platen, and the upper end was positioned to contact a platen connected to the test machine. The compression load was increased at a constant rate until the ultimate failure of the test panel occurred. A typical test set-up is shown in Figure 5.

Strain and load outputs were gathered by a data acquisition system (Sciometric System 200) and recorded by a computer. Selected gauge outputs were monitored to verify that the load distribution in the panel was uniform. The shadow Moiré technique was used to monitor buckling patterns and any delamination during the test.

DISCUSSION OF PREDICTED AND TEST RESULTS

INITIAL BUCKLING LOADS

The initial buckling loads were determined from the load-strain curves as the load at which either the readings from the back-to-back strain gauges began to separate or the point of sudden change in the slope of the curve. The initial buckling load was also estimated from the shadow Moiré fringe patterns and the load-deflection curve and the results from these three techniques agreed well. The end shortening of the panel is plotted against the loading history in Figure 4. Figure 4 shows that at the beginning of the test there is a linear relationship between the load and deflection. A significant change in this relationship occurs at a load of about 114 kN which indicates the start of skin buckling in the two bays. The skin on the two free edges buckles at a much lower load as indicated by the finite element analysis, however this initial buckling does not change the global behaviour of the whole panel. The linear buckling analysis predicted that the local buckling loads for the edges and the bays were 73 kN and 124 kN, respectively. The latter was 8.8 % higher than the experimental result of 114 kN.

The experimental strains and predicted strains for a location in the bay are plotted against load in Figure 6, which shows a reasonably good agreement of the post-buckling response. In addition, both the test and analysis curves start separation at a load of about 73 kN which indicates the initial buckling of the skin on the two free edges. A significant separation occurs on both curves at a load of about 118 kN which is recognized as the buckling of the skin in the bay.

FAILURE LOADS, STRAINS AND MODES

The panel failed at a load of 289.1 kN. and the predicted failure load was 293 kN. see Figure 3. By comparing predicted and experimental results in Figure 6, the initial buckling loads and the post-buckling response from these two plots agreed very well.

During the testing, 4 contours were initially developed in each bay at an average load of 124.7 kN and then gradually evolved into 7 contours in each bay as the load increased, see Figure 7.

Many researchers [2,3,4,5] reported that the failure of a post-buckled panel has been attributed to the separation of the stiffeners from the skin. In this study, the failed panel exhibited that the stiffeners were disbanded from the skin, however the panel failure was so explosive and destructive that it was difficult to record how failure was initiated during the test. By examining the failed panel, the failure mode was associated with compression failure of the caps, local delamination (disbonding) in the flange-skin intersection and failure along the 45° lines in the skin. The maximum strain measured in the test panel was less than 0.6 % (5911 microstrain). Prior to the failure of the panel, partial separation of the flange from the skin was observed as a sudden change in the shadow Moiré pattern and some audible noises were heard, but it is noted that the separations (delaminations) appeared to be local in nature. The final failure load of the

panel was approximately 2.5 times higher than its skin buckling load at the bays. This demonstrated that the panels performed with post-buckled capabilities.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Simple techniques have been developed to efficiently lay up plies for stiffener elements and built-up composite structure.
2. Comparison of the magnitude of initial skin buckling and ultimate load indicated that the panels exhibited a good capability to carry load well beyond the onset of local buckling, i.e. good post-buckled performance.
3. The technique using the bending moment of the stiffener to predict the failure load of the panel worked very well in this study.
4. The predicted and experimental initial buckling and failure loads were in good agreement.

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Table 1. Material Properties of IM6/5245C (R.T.)

0° Tensile Modulus (GPa)	180.5
0° Compressive Modulus (GPa)	147.7
90° Tensile Modulus (GPa)	8.86
90° Tensile Modulus (GPa)	7.34
±45° Shear Modulus (GPa)	5.66
0° Tensile Poisson Ratio	0.31
0° Compressive Poisson Ratio	0.36

Figure 1. Panel Geometry, dimensions and stacking sequences

Figure 2. Finite element model

Figure 3. Bending moment on stiffener vs load

Figure 4. Load-axial displacement curve

Figure 5. Test set-up

Figure 7. Shadow Moiré pattern of panel under load of 270 kN

Figure 6. Strains in skin